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Data Management Plan

EU's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme

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UNIVERSITY
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Executive Summary

This document outlines the *Data Management Plan (DMP)* for the *project SPECification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data (SPEARHEAD)*, funded by the Horizon Europe framework programme of the European Union (EU). It details the project's data management policy and provides essential information about all datasets that will be produced and processed during the project. The DMP defines the guidelines to manage all data assets generated/used by the project under the **FAIR principles**, in order to achieve to the maximum extent possible the *Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse* of the project's data products. The DMP will be continuously updated to match ongoing progress and monitor adherence to the established open data management policy throughout the project. The current version represents the status at the end of the preparatory phase, six months into the project.

The DMP covers: (i) the types of data, formats, and metadata to be collected, processed, and/or generated; (ii) the methodologies and protocols to be applied for data management and processing; (iii) the methods and repositories for making all data openly accessible; (iv) strategies to enhance data interoperability and reusability.

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1 Introduction

The *SPeCification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data* (SPEARHEAD) project is a three year-long Research and Innovation action funded by the Horizon Europe framework programme of the European Union (EU). The SPEARHEAD project focuses on high energy particles, originating either from the Sun (i.e., Solar Energetic Particles – SEPs) or our Galaxy (Galactic Cosmic Rays – GCRs). SPEARHEAD will address several open scientific questions on the physical processes governing the acceleration, release and propagation of such particles in the inner heliosphere. SPEARHEAD undertakes an innovative and synergistic approach that will foster the coordinated exploitation of energetic particle and context data from European missions and instruments, in conjunction with international missions, to maximize the scientific return and to enable new research activities. In doing so, SPEARHEAD will openly provide to the scientific community

- novel, high-level data products based on recalibrations of radiation monitor data - on so far unreleased data from science-grade instruments, and measurements of ground-based neutron monitors;
- technical notes on the response functions of several science-grade and monitoring instruments, utilizing Geant4 modelling;
- comprehensive catalogues of near-relativistic ions and relativistic electrons in strong SEP/GLE events as well as FD (Forbush Decrease) events from a fleet of different instruments onboard spacecraft, at radial distances from 0.04 to 5 AU (Astronomical Units);
- scientific and data analysis as well as tools enabling the coordinated analysis of high energy particle data with context observations.

This deliverable is the first report on the project's Data Management Plan (DMP), which will be updated with ongoing progress in the course of the project. Its purpose is to establish the principles and guidelines of the project's data management policy, as well as to provide an initial registry of the datasets anticipated to be used or generated by the project. In the rest of the document, (i) the next part of the introductory section links the project's objectives with its expected outputs, (ii) Section 2 describes the methodology adopted to construct the DMP, (iii) Section 3 includes detailed descriptions of the anticipated datasets based on the templates provided in the Argos community tool (<https://argos.openaire.eu/home>) for projects under the Horizon Europe framework, and (iv) Section 4 provides the concluding remarks.

1.1 Project's objectives and expected outputs

The connections between SPEARHEAD project's scope and objectives, as per Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, to the project's research activities and expected outputs, are identified in this section. Table 1 below maps Work Package (WP) and Task descriptions to the corresponding objectives anticipated by the project, as outlined in the Description of Action (DoA). An overview of the specific data products expected by particular WP activities can be found in this table.

Table 1. Mapping of project's objectives and expected outputs.

SPEARHEAD WP	SPEARHEAD Task	Objective	Corresponding section in DoA Part B
WP1 Management	Task 1.2 Management and reporting ... <i>Additionally, a Data Management Plan (DMP, D1.2), will be drafted, maintained and continuously updated throughout the project, supported by WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6 and WP7. The DMP shall detail the</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide the project with efficient management and communication IT systems 	

	<i>method(s), protocols, data and higher-data products of SPEARHEAD. It will further describe the principles of the adopted fully open data policy, approaches and procedures for data and metadata production and storage, as well as the methodology needed and developed for accessing the data.</i>		
WP2 Instrument Response	<p>Task 2-1. Construction of (updated) Geant4 models</p> <p>Task 2-2. Computation of instrument response functions</p> <p>Task 2-3. Update of the response function of NM to low-energy particles</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide detailed documentation on the Geant4 simulation for the science-grade instruments providing high-energy data to SPEARHEAD ● Provide validated response functions for the above instruments. ● Provide an update of the neutron-monitor yield function in the low-energy range 	1.2.2
WP3 Cross- & re- calibration	<p>Task 3-1 Reanalysis/recalibration of SREM proton measurements from SREM unit</p> <p>Task 3-2 Cross-calibration of NOAA GOES HEPAD data with IMP-8/GME</p> <p>Task 3-3. Cross-calibration between ground-based and space-borne dataset</p> <p>Task 3-4. The use of low-orbiting spectrometers AMS-02 and PAMELA to calibrate and validate space-borne Measurements</p> <p>Task 3-5. Cross-calibration between Integral single detector counters and differential particle flux dataset</p> <p>Task 3-6. EPHIN as Photon detector</p> <p>Task 3-7. ERNE and SIXS as a relativistic particle instrument</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide SEP and GCR SREM flux dataset ● Provide cross-calibrated NOAA GOES HEPAD proton flux dataset ● Provide calibration curves for ground-based NMs using low-orbiting spectrometers. ● Provide GCR and SEP single detector derived flux dataset for SOHO and Chandra EPHIN ● Provide Photon time profiles from 	1.2.3

	<p>Task 3-8. EPHIN, HET and KET as a relativistic particle instrument</p>	<p>the single detector measurement of EPHIN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide SEP and GCR flux spectra based on the ΔE-ΔE- and ΔE-C-method from SOHO and Chandra EPHIN and Ulysses KET. ● Provide relativistic particle fluxes and anisotropies of SOHO / ERNE / HED ● Provide ultra relativistic electron fluxes from Ulysses KET 	
<p>WP4 Context Observations</p>	<p>Task 4-1. Establishing a list of CME events to be modelled in Tasks 4.2 and 4.3</p> <p>Task 4-2. Identifications of radio, hard X-rays and gamma-ray signatures of the strong CME events</p> <p>Task 4-3. Three-dimensional modelling of CME shocks</p> <p>Task 4-4: Three-dimensional modelling of CME flux ropes</p> <p>Task 4-5: Comparison of modelled shock waves and flux ropes with in situ measurement</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide key properties of coronal shocks, based on context observations and related modelling, for high-energy SEP events analysed in detail in SPEARHEAD. ● Provide solar hard X-ray and gamma-ray observations for the high energy SEP events analysed in detail in SPEARHEAD. ● Provide the structure of ICMEs for the detailed analysis of energetic particle transport during SEP events and Forbush decreases analysed in detail in SPEARHEAD. ● Provide a 	<p>1.2.4</p>

		comprehensive list of large-scale solar-wind structures during all events catalogued in SPEARHEAD.	
WP5 Scientific Data Analysis	<p>Task 5-1. Analysis of >100 MeV proton events</p> <p>Task 5-2. Analysis of ultrarelativistic solar electron events</p> <p>Task 5-3. Analysis of sub-GLE events</p> <p>Task 5-4. ICME-related Forbush decreases</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Compile lists of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - high-energy SEP events: ultrarelativistic electron events, >100 MeV proton events and sub-GLEs - ICME-related Forbush decreases 	1.2.5
WP6 Data Products & Tool Development	<p>Task 6-1: SPEARHEAD tools and data development plan</p> <p>Task 6-2: Distributing SPEARHEAD data products</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Coordinate the SPEARHEAD tool development and data product distribution ● Generate the interfaces necessary to ensure effective distribution of the SPEARHEAD tools and high-level datasets. 	1.2.6

2 Methodology

The methodology adopted for the design of the DMP is based on two pillars: (i) the guidelines¹ provided by the European Commission on FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) Data Management in Horizon 2020, and (ii) open access policy in accordance with the H2020 guidelines² regarding Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data. The FAIR principles³ were established in 2016 by the FORCE 11 group⁴ to determine the best practices in research data preparation for both humans and machines. The rest of this section is organized to expose FAIR data principles in the management of SPEARHEAD data products and publications, under the adopted open access policy.

2.1 Findability

SPEARHEAD will use the Zenodo repository maintained by CERN as the main tool to render the project's research data findable. As a first step, a SPEARHEAD community has been established in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/spearhead/>), enabling the upload of all public datasets and catalogues generated through the project as well as scientific publications and presentations to this community (Figure-1). All these products will be further registered in the European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE) community. High level datasets and catalogues uploaded in Zenodo will be assigned with Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) and enriched with metadata, including Grant Number and Project Acronym. In parallel, version control is provided by the repository. The project's virtual server, will be the repository where all data products will be kept and rendered publicly accessible. For higher level data of a specific mission/instrument, the corresponding naming conventions applied to the (meta)data will be preserved.

Figure-1 - The Zenodo Community of SPEARHEAD

¹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation (2016). Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020.

² European Commission. Horizon 2020 Programme. Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020.

³ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

⁴ <https://force11.org/>

2.2 Accessibility

High level (Level 3 – L3) data products and compiled event catalogues produced by the project will be distributed via data servers hosted at the partner institutes. NOA has established a virtual server, hosted within the National Data Center (NDC) service in order to meet the needs of SPEARHEAD, as detailed in D8.1. The server will collect all products of the project and will be maintained thereafter by NDC. Access to the server is managed by NOA and is currently restricted to the project’s partners.

The SPEARHEAD project promotes open science principles in all its activities. All data and tools generated by the project will be publicly distributed through a variety of avenues to maximize their impact. Datasets and catalogues will be made available on unrestricted websites with copies integrated into the ESA and NASA archives where possible. Data products will further be released through instrument Principal Investigator (PI) teams’ websites. SPEARHEAD high-energy particle data and catalogues will also be integrated to other data analysis services. AMDA (amda.cdpp.eu) is an interactive database that can be used to visualize and analyze in situ data from a large number of space missions. Calibrated data on high energy particles as well as SPEARHEAD catalogues of SEPs and ICMEs will also be integrated in the AMDA database. The ESAC Science Data Centre (ESDC, www.cosmos.esa.int/web/esdc/about) maintains the majority of the space science mission archives for ESA missions. SPEARHEAD will integrate its high-level data products with ESDC, whenever possible. SEPServer (utu.sepserver.eu) is a tool developed in an FP7 project by the same name (2010–2013), hosting a set of catalogues, data and plotting tools for SEP events. The SEP event lists generated by SPEARHEAD will be ingested to SEPServer, to increase the findability and accessibility of SPEARHEAD data by its users. To further ensure the accessibility of its data products, SPEARHEAD will also release (mainly) Python software tools in a public GitHub repository, as explained in D6.1. In addition, SPEARHEAD will further aim at utilizing large-scale open access infrastructures such as ESA Datalabs (<https://datalabs.esa.int>) to share data and tools with the broader scientific community.

Figure-2 - The ESA Datalabs main page

2.3 Interoperability

SPEARHEAD will provide detailed documentation along with each dataset, as descriptive metadata containing relevant information to the specific dataset. Naming conventions of the source missions will be preserved, as well as the corresponding data vocabularies. Data products from SPEARHEAD will be provided in binary CDF, NetCDF or FITS format, as suggested by the International Heliophysics

Data Environment Alliance⁵ (IHDEA), since these are the main standard file formats of the international heliophysics community. Further enhancing interoperability, SPEARHEAD plans to follow the International Solar-Terrestrial Physics (ISTP) guidelines for data and metadata in CDF files. These have been adopted by the Interagency Consultative Group (IACG) as well as by most heliophysics missions, making them compatible with most existing analysis and plotting tools and online databases.

2.4 Reusability

All datasets generated by the project, along with the corresponding documentation on their contents and software tools for data loading, visualization and analysis will be made openly available in trusted public repositories. Datasets with typical tabular format will be provided in easy-to-read CSV format, while the project's software tools will cover data loading in cases of more complex formats. These higher level products will be disseminated through the project's website⁶, scientific publications and the project's presence in community conferences and workshops. As a result, the further re-use of these datasets by the scientific community is greatly promoted and facilitated.

2.5 Allocation of resources

The necessary resources to manage the project's data under the FAIR principles will be covered by the EU SPEARHEAD Horizon Europe funding, and further supported by infrastructures of the partner institutes. In addition, scientific publications will be made open access in the Zenodo and arXiv repositories, which are free of charge. The extent of openly accessible publications in international refereed journals will be dictated by the dissemination budget.

The Consortium Board (CB) oversees data management, with the Project Management Board handling the majority of managerial duties (see D8.1).

Resources for long term preservation of access to the data and products underline the open access policy applied throughout SPEARHEAD. For instance, storage of data in ESA and NASA archives for which costs are under their responsibility guarantees stability and long-term access to the data products. Additionally, stability and long term access is further enhanced via the utilization of Zenodo, maintained by CERN, as a repository for e.g. catalogued data and files (in e.g. CSV format). Software tools written in open access programming language (i.e. Python) will be submitted to repositories at GitHub⁷ as well, further ensuring long-term preservation of results from the project. All service applications, data and tools that are developed in SPEARHEAD are hosted at the cloud facilities made available by the NDC in Greece and by the individual project's research organizations. Also, the PI websites belong to the same category. For those resources, long-term stability is harder to guarantee, as it requires either a level of basic funding or is subject to renewal.

⁵ <https://ihdea.net>

⁶ <https://spearhead-he.eu/>

⁷ <https://github.com/spearhead-he>

3 Dataset descriptions

The anticipated datasets to be used/generated by the project are listed in this section. Following the H2020 templates available in the Argos open access platform (<https://argos.openaire.eu/home>), any information on the datasets regarding data types, format, size and attributes will be documented in the dataset's description. Table 2 provides a list of these datasets, while the first entry (Calibrated Datasets - Ulysses/KET) is linked to the corresponding draft Argos description in the Annex, as an example. *The DMP will be constantly updated with additional information on the datasets as the project progresses.* The Argos tool will be utilized to generate and export these updated versions of the DMP.

Figure 3 - The Argos open access platform

Table 2. Datasets to be generated by the project.

SPEARHEAD WP	Dataset	Short name
WP3	Annex I: Calibrated Datasets - Ulysses/KET	Particle-Flux-KET
WP3	Calibrated datasets – SOHO/ERNE	
WP3	Calibrated Datasets - EPHIN - single detector	SOHO-EPHIN-SINGLE-DETECTOR-DATA-SET
WP3	Calibrated Datasets – ESA SREM	
WP3	Calibrated Datasets – NOAA GOES HEPAD	
WP3	Calibrated Datasets – SoHO/HET	

WP3	Calibrated Datasets – SolO/HET – single detector	
WP3	Calibrated Datasets – Chandra & SOHO/EPHIN	
WP3	Calibrated Datasets – BepiColombo/SIXS	
WP4	List of CME-ICME events	
WP5	Catalogue of ultra-relativistic electrons	URSEE-Catalogue-SPEARHEAD
WP5	Catalogue of >100 MeV Protons	
WP5	SEP events observed by SolO at 1MeV electrons & 10MeV protons	
WP5	List of ICME-related Forbush Decreases	

4 Conclusions

The *first version* of the **Data Management Plan (DMP)** of the *SPEARHEAD project* that constitutes **Deliverable 1.2** (D1.2) of the project is detailed in this document. D1.2 is a living document and will be updated throughout the project for each of the periodic reviews as well as for the final review.

References

D8.1 Project Website, 29-02-2024, SPEARHEAD Deliverable

D6.1 SPEARHEAD Tools and Data Development Plan, 30-06-2024, SPEARHEAD Deliverable

List of Acronyms/Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AMS	Alpha Magnetic Spectrometer
AU	Astronomical Units
CDAWeb	Coordinated Data Analysis Web
CDF	Common Data Format
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EPHIN	Electron Proton Helium Instrument
ERNE	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron
ESA	European Space Agency
ESAC	European Space Astronomy Center
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
FD	Forbush Decrease
GCR	Galactic Cosmic Ray
GLE	Ground Level Enhancement
GME	Goddard Medium Energy
GOES	Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite
HEPAD	High Energy Proton and Alpha Detector

HET	High Energy Telescope
ICME	Interplanetary CME
IHDEA	International Heliophysics Data Environment Alliance
IMP	Interplanetary Monitoring Platform
ISTP	International Solar-Terrestrial Physics
KET	Kiel Electron Telescope
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
N/A	Not Available
N/K	Not Known
PAMELA	Payload for Antimatter Matter Exploration and Light-nuclei Astrophysics
PI	Principal Investigator
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SIXS	Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SREM	Standard Radiation Environment Monitor
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
N/A	Not Available
N/K	Not Known
NM	Neutron Monitor
TBD	To be determined
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

Annexes

Annex I: Calibrated Datasets - Ulysses/KET (Example dataset)

Brief description of the dataset

The Kiel Electron Telescope (KET) is part of the Ulysses COsmic ray and Solar Particle INvestigation (COSPIN) experiment, which has been described in detail by Simpson et al. [1992]. The instrument is designed to measure electron, proton and Helium-particle fluxes in several energy windows ranging from a few MeV/n up to and above a few GeV/n. The Ulysses COSPIN/KET instrument has been described in [Simpson et al. \(1992\)](#) and [Ferrando et al. \(1996\)](#).

It measures protons and helium in the energy range from 6 MeV/nucleon to above 2 GeV/nucleon and electrons in the energy range from 3 MeV to a few GeV using two silicon detectors, an aerogel Cherenkov detector and PBF2-calorimeter.

D1 and D2 are 0.5 mm thick semiconductor detectors, C1 is an aerogel Cherenkov-detector and A a plastic anticoincidence scintillator. C2 is a lead fluoride Cherenkov-detector, S1 and S2 are plastic scintillators. Functionally, the detector system consists of two parts: an entrance telescope and a calorimeter, surrounded by a guard counter A.

- The entrance telescope is composed of a silica-aerogel Cherenkov-detector C1 inserted between semiconductor detectors, D1 and D2. Together with the guard counter A, this combination determines the geometry, selects particles with velocity $\beta > 0.938$ and determines the particle charge.
- The calorimeter consists of a 2.5 radiation length lead-fluoride (PbF₂) crystal used as Cherenkov-detector (C2) and a scintillator S2. The calorimeter consists of a lead-fluoride crystal in which the electron shower develops, and a scintillator cup S2 to detect particles not absorbed in C2.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

The raw data have been taken by the Ulysses KET until 2009. Modeling of the Instrument leads to new fluxes that are provided here for the first time.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

The data set is derived from the raw data set from the KET

1.1.5 What is its format?

CDF format

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Size of the dataset will be determined during the course of the processing of the raw data

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To improve a product

Raw data from the KET are not suitable for SEP event analysis. Combination of raw data with model input allows to derive the physical quantities.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

DLR funded project

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education
- The public

Researchers/research community: Unique data set for SEP investigations

Education: Example of a complex measurement and its modeling

Public: Space weather radiation impact

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

Yes

All publications referenced in

<https://www.cosmos.esa.int/documents/405305/405450/udsket.pdf/bdf843ce-67bd-46ca-a35c-9ada7b747925>

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

All data are publicly available in e.g. PI servers and ESA archives

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

Tools to read CDF data files, e.g. <https://spacepy.github.io/pycdf.html>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Organizations identifiers
- Project identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

This will be added after processing

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

<https://zenodo.org/>

SPEARHEAD repository

Dataset will be made available on unrestricted websites with copies integrated into the ESA and NASA archives where possible.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Has an open access content policy

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

Generation of SPEARHEAD Community in Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/communities/spearhead/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

In communication with ESA

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

DOI

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Depends in the repository (for example Zenodo provides versioning)

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Particle-Flux-KET

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open access

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Tools to read CDF data files

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

Several e.g python loader

<https://spacepy.github.io/pycdf.html>

3.2.2.7 Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.

Python or other programming languages

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Several archives (e.g. PI institute, ESA, NASA, Zenodo archives)

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The NDC will also host the dataset for at least 2 years after the project's end date

Incorporation to Zenodo and ESA, NASA archives which is planned in the course of the project facilitates long term accessibility

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output cannot be openly shared?

Yes, however the dataset will be shared

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

Generation of CDF data / NASA, ISTEP/IACG guidelines

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

This calibrated dataset is linked to the raw KET dataset and the Geant4 Simulation model for KET.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Non-Commercial)

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

Data are archived on Zenodo and depends on funding of the corresponding facilities

See also 3.2.2.10

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Other

Check with calibration measurements

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

This is the outcome of an EU funded project thus the cost is included in the fund

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

This is the outcome of an EU funded project thus the cost is included in the fund

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Marlon Koeberle (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9751-8137>)

Bernd Heber (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0960-5658>)

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall
- Other

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

No

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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